

Call for Action!

Sustaining Dutch strength in European Life and Medical Science (LMS) research infrastructures

A collective perspective on the long-term sustainability of national participation in European LMS research infrastructures

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Executive Summary

As part of European Life and Medical Science Research Infrastructures (LMS RIs), 15 Dutch research infrastructures directly contribute to more than 20 high-priority national policy agendas across five ministries. As advanced infrastructures, they underpin national research and provide avenues for synergy and efficiency by diminishing the need for national (and local) investments. Altogether, the research infrastructures offer great value for Dutch society. This value is under pressure because the infrastructures rely on competitive short-term project funding. Without a sustained national investment commitment, these RIs are unable to meet their scientific and societal mandate for the Netherlands.

As 15 LMS research infrastructures, we step up to realise a next level of integrated service provisioning to all life science and medical science communities in the Netherlands. We are committed to help design a national LMS-RI coordination and support mechanism and help realise a collaborative level of strategy, organisation, outreach and life cycle management of our RIs. We are dedicated to help secure sustained international quality, effectiveness, visibility and value of the Dutch research infrastructure landscape to science and society through our active participation of the European LMS research infrastructures.

We call on our government and funders to:

1. Acknowledge the scientific, social, and economic value to our society of the active Dutch participation in European LMS Research Infrastructures.
2. Help sustain participation of the Netherlands in European LMS Research

Infrastructures, by securing the necessary national investments.

3. Support the advancement of coordination of national LMS research infrastructures via a *national LMS-RI coordination and support mechanism*.

“We call for action by all stakeholders involved – government, funders and research performing organisations – to come to a collective arrangement to secure long-term national participation in the European LMS RIs.”

We call on research organisations to:

1. Acknowledge the value of strong participation in European LMS Research Infrastructures to the quality of the Dutch health and life sciences research and education field.
2. Help establish a collaborative roadmap towards a strong and integrated portfolio of Dutch LMS research infrastructures that includes a sustainable mechanism to participate in European LMS RIs and make effective use of European resources.
3. Help build a strategic collective research infrastructure as part of a *national LMS-RI coordination and support mechanism*, by capitalising on the strong existing infrastructure components contributed by individual research organisations.

1.

Introduction

1. Introduction

Strong and frontrunning research infrastructures are an important asset for research. They are a prerequisite to drive and advance science in the Netherlands to contribute to critical policy domains and innovations in our society and address strategic challenges in areas such as sustainability and public health. Here, research depends on infrastructures of high quality and well rooted in the European research infrastructure ecosystem.

“All European LMS Research infrastructures bring together research resources at a scale beyond individual organisations and even countries.”

The broad Dutch Life and Medical Sciences (LMS) field builds on an extensive range of advanced research technologies and resources (e.g. collections and data) to analyse, model and interpret scientific and societal data across health and life sciences disciplines. As for all other science domains, it is imperative to tie the national LMS research infrastructure capacities to those developed by expert centres internationally. This allows for continuous feedback on international advancements related to these infrastructure

capacities, and how they can optimally strengthen research in the Netherlands. It also allows for Dutch strengths to be disseminated globally.

1.1 European LMS research infrastructures catalyse Dutch science

Within the framework of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)² the Netherlands currently participates in 15 European LMS research infrastructures, each assembling key facilities and resources for specific areas of the life and medical sciences fields (Table 1). In its recent portfolio analysis, NWO evaluated and mapped the international LMS RIs by ‘systems level’ in biology research, illustrated in Figure 1 below³.

The majority of these infrastructures have meanwhile matured into so-called *Landmark* infrastructures serving scientists across Europe, while some have started in recent years or are in the preparatory process of formal organisation towards strategic European research infrastructures. All European LMS Research infrastructures bring together research resources at a scale beyond individual organisations and even countries. They also provide advanced capabilities that support a broad range of research fields, as illustrated in Table 1 for the infrastructures providing access to specialised bioimaging facilities.

² <https://www.esfri.eu/health-food> and <https://www.esfri.eu/environment>

³ NWO report: Analysis of the Dutch participation in international research infrastructures, Dec. 2023

Table 1: List of the 15 European LMS Research Infrastructures with Dutch participation and the key capacities they assemble across European research centres. Infrastructures are listed in line with the Roadmap Large scale Research Infrastructures for the LMS field.

	<p>DiSSCo: Biodiversity reference libraries and data management, specimen digitization, data integration.</p>
	<p>EMPHASIS: Plant phenotyping, genetic analysis, environmental interaction studies.</p>
	<p>eLTER: Ecosystem monitoring, long-term ecological research, data harmonization.</p>
	<p>IBISBA: Industrial biotechnology, synthetic biology, bioengineering.</p>
	<p>LifeWatch: Biodiversity informatics, ecological modelling, data services for biodiversity research.</p>
	<p>MIRRI: Microbial resource management, microbiology research, strain preservation.</p>
	<p>BBMRI: Biobanking, biological sample quality management, data sharing in biomedicine.</p>
	<p>EATRIS: Translational research, biomarker validation, drug development.</p>
	<p>EBRAINS: Neuroscience data, brain research, computational modelling</p>
	<p>EIRENE: Enabling exposome research, exploring environmental risk factors for health</p>

Figure 1 (below): Position of the 15 European LMS Research Infrastructures with Dutch participation according to the thematic organisation of the NWO-LIFE research agenda. The colour-coded category assignment corresponds with the clustering of RIs that is used in the national Roadmap Large-Scale Research Facilities overseen by the Permanent Committee Large-Scale Research Facilities (PC-GWI).

IMAGING TECHNOLOGY

Several European LMS RIs offer advanced imaging technologies, offering deep insights into both micro and macro environments.

Photo: Skeleton head of a toad
Source: *Naturalis Biodiversity Center*

In molecular biology, imaging techniques like X-ray crystallography and cryo-electron microscopy enable scientists to visualize the structures of molecules at atomic resolution, which is crucial for understanding their functions and interactions. Additionally, fluorescence and confocal microscopy allow researchers to pinpoint the localization of these molecules within cells, shedding light on cellular processes and disease mechanisms.

In medicine, imaging technologies like MRI, CT scans, and ultrasound are indispensable for diagnosing and monitoring diseases in living organisms. These tools provide detailed views of tissues, organs, and tumours, aiding in early detection and treatment planning.

Photo: Structure of SARS-CoV-2 virus
Source: *Unsplash (CCO public domain license)*

Moreover, imaging is essential in biodiversity studies and conservation. High-resolution imaging of species in collections allows scientists to document, compare, and study biodiversity, helping understand ecological dynamics and counter the loss of biodiversity.

These imaging technologies collectively advance scientific knowledge, assist in innovation and help in policy development in important societal dossiers.

Photo: Fluorescence image of mouse embryo
Source: *Wikipedia Commons*

Figure 2: Examples of access to advanced technology capacities offered through European LMS Research Infrastructures. A range of complementary advanced technologies in the bioimaging field offered by Eurobioimaging, INSTRUMENT, ERINHA, and EBRAINS opens new avenues of research in a broad range of the LMS research fields underlying important policy dossiers.

1.2 Dutch research facilities help shape the European LMS RIs

European LMS infrastructures all build on scientific and technical strength already built up in the participating countries. This also holds for the Dutch field of research performing organisations, that have developed indispensable assets to take part in international research infrastructure programmes. Participating expert facilities and resources from labs in the Netherlands have often been co-funded through dedicated funding calls, such as in the framework of the national infrastructure Roadmap overseen by the Permanent Committee for Large-scale Research Infrastructures (PC-GWI). In parallel, the programme *Faciliteiten Toegestemd Onderzoek* adds infrastructure capacity to the applied research organisations.

Typically, individual research infrastructures in the LMS field operate in a distributed model, often organised in a hub and nodes structure with a European Research Infrastructure coordination centre (hub) and national ‘nodes’ in the participating countries. The Dutch national nodes in the European LMS infrastructures involve the key players in their respective national research community. Together, they engage in structural international collaboration to connect cross-border to peer institutes to jointly realise essential European research infrastructures. They provide access to international data repositories, collections and high-end research facilities, standards and expertise that exceeds the sum of what each of the members can provide. Through the international network established, the infrastructures often pave the way to jointly participate in international project and programme calls (European and beyond), offering funding opportunities for research and development.

2.

European LMS RIs as cornerstones for science to deliver on national policy dossiers

2. European LMS RIs as cornerstones for science to deliver on national policy dossiers

Major societal challenges in the scope of the life and medical sciences can only be addressed by a collaborative cross border strategy. The European Strategy Forum on research infrastructures has created a [long-term strategic research infrastructure agenda](#) to help society meet these challenges. In this framework, the European LMS RIs are the cornerstones of an advanced research ecosystem to address challenges encountered in life and medical sciences. They have been set up to strengthen pan-European collaboration for the advancement of science and help strengthen European research and knowledge development in a value system aiming to promote public health and quality of life in the broadest sense. Importantly, these infrastructures deliver to national policy dossiers in a sustainable way, beyond the level of programmes and projects, through science and innovation supporting governments, and informing strategic policy domains at European and national levels.

2.1 Important national policy dossiers as drivers for the LMS field

A broad range of national strategic policy areas depend on European/international collaboration in science, technology and innovation. Domains such as (public) health and medicine, sustainability as well as climate adaptiveness and resilience, all depend on evidence-driven projections, fed by integrated data that can be accessed and re-used for interpretation. Similarly, technological and industrial innovation gain strength from access to collections of well-structured data and biomaterials, high-end scientific instrumentation, and international

collaboration. These assets depend on long-term and sustained investments in infrastructures, tooling and collaborations, and it would be impossible to establish these by short-term initiatives and investments. In fact, their very existence provides the bedding where initiatives in science, technology and innovation can flow and flourish.

“The Dutch Life and Medical Science research infrastructures (LMS RIs), as part of 15 European LMS research infrastructures, directly contribute to more than 20 high-priority national policy agendas across Dutch ministries, offering great value for the Dutch society”

Through their participation in European RIs, the national LMS infrastructures thus not only provide essential local and pan-European open scientific infrastructure and services to a diverse circle of (inter)national users, they are also essential for science-supported national strategic policy implementation. These include important topics such as biodiversity, resilience of ecosystems, sustainable food production, public health/OneHealth (incl. pandemic preparedness and exposure to harmful compounds (exposome)), healthcare innovation, access to data and collections, data stewardship and digital technologies (including responsible AI). These societal challenges translate to policy domains governed by different national ministries as outlined in Figure 3 below.

Ministry of Economic Affairs	Biomolecular & cell technologies - Imaging technologies - AI & Data
Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management	Biotechnology, Compliance & safe by design - Water management & food production - Climate change & sustainability
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport	Health care innovation – Patient’s privacy - Public health & one health - Psychoactive compounds - Biotechnology & biosecurity
Ministry of Education, Culture and Science	Dutch Research Agenda (NWA) - Large Scale RIs (Inter)National Policy
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Food Security and Nature	Sustainable agriculture, food safety & security - Nature conservation & biodiversity - One health

Figure 3: The Dutch Life and Medical Science research infrastructures (LMS RIs), as part of 15 European LMS research infrastructures, directly contribute to more than 20 high-priority national policy agendas across Dutch ministries, offering great value for the Dutch society. Further details of the link of individual research infrastructures to policy dossiers are provided in Annex 1.

2.2 European LMS Research Infrastructures can help countries to respond to immediate policy challenges

The European LMS RIs – and involved national research infrastructures – are complementary in what they deliver to support strategic national policy domains and collaborate where feasible to enable scientific advancements

across disciplines. In a [shared position paper](#), a broad group of 14 European LMS RIs recently voiced their commitment to support European policy priorities through their collective capacities to strengthen science & innovation at a European scale.

ISIDORE and BY-COVID: How European RIs joined forces for sustainable pandemic preparedness and resilience

Spring 2021, the European Commission set up an emergency infrastructure call and awarded 21M€ to the pan-European **ISIDORE** consortium, led by [ERINHA](#), in February 2022.

Strategically, this project links relevant research infrastructures in the Life and Medical sciences for sustainable future collaboration. ISIDORE provides and develops multidisciplinary research services for rapid responses to COVID-19 and other infectious disease epidemics (specialised biosafety labs, biobanks, advanced technologies, and more).

Together, the ~160 organisations involved develop innovative multidisciplinary research models and services and provide access to research facilities that any scientist can apply for. European grants are available for transnational access, providing enhanced opportunities for international and collaborative pandemic research.

Coordinated by [ELIXIR](#), the **BeYond-COVID** project aimed to make COVID-19 data and data from other infectious diseases FAIR and openly accessible to scientists, medical staff and policy makers.

Building on capacities of 10 European LMS RIs, and co-led by ELIXIR, BY-COVID realised an Open global COVID Data Platform. This offered a framework for making data easier to access, aggregate and analyse to enable scientists in academia and industry to respond faster to new SARS-CoV-2 strains or other pathogens causing infectious diseases.

The BY-COVID infrastructure helped policy-makers assess the impact of COVID-19 and take appropriate measures to protect people globally. Its open science approach strongly facilitates open innovation in academia and industry to help fight infectious diseases.

Jointly, the ISIDORE and BYCOVID consortia of LMS research infrastructures contributed significantly to conquer the worldwide COVID-19 pandemic and help strengthen pandemic preparedness across Europe.

Figure 4: Two examples of how European LMS RIs have jointly enabled to respond rapidly to the Covid-19 pandemic by opening essential research and data resources for scientists and policy makers across the world.

3.

Sustainability model involving all stakeholders

3. Sustainability model involving all stakeholders

The Netherlands currently lacks a comprehensive strategy and arrangement among all stakeholders to design and sustain the national participation in the European LMS Research infrastructures, especially when it comes to funding the national membership contributions. The current project-based approach to cover international membership jeopardises the sustained participation in these strategic research infrastructures. Apart from the continuous hassle of arranging temporary funding, this lack of sustainable funding mechanism has a negative impact on the strategic development of a strong national LMS research infrastructure landscape.

We call upon the Dutch Government, funding agencies, universities and research institutions to collectively take responsibility for the sustainable, stable operation of and participation in European LMS RIs that are essential for a competitive Dutch scientific landscape. Maximising the impact of participation thereby needs a common strategy and collective long-term arrangement that builds on consistent dedication of scientific communities through high-quality in-kind contribution and mature national coordination processes.

3.1 International membership needs national commitment

For each individual European LMS research infrastructure, the cross-national collaboration among European countries is organised legally by establishing a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) or related construct⁴. This construct arranges the

international governance, as well as the legal, financial and administrative framework to guide the collective membership of participating countries. International memberships require support and commitment at national level.

Each individual infrastructure consortium also has agreed upon a shared funding model, mostly building on an agreed annual membership fee of the participating countries. For most European LMS RIs, these national memberships are arranged through commitments at the level of national ministries of science and education. National governments thus formally sign up for the national participation, confirming the national financial contribution to strengthen the respective infrastructures.

At the national level, funding of the participation in long-term European research infrastructures cannot be dependent on competitive national project funding calls, or sudden changes in priorities at the level of Dutch academic organisations. Instead, they need to be strategically solid for significant periods of time, to ensure sustainability of important large-scale international infrastructures. As part of a necessary broader and collective arrangement with the field of stakeholders in the LMS domain, we foresee that the best, and only viable, approach is a model with funding of national memberships fully provided by the government.

While it is clear that the LMS research infrastructures provide direct value for science, we have shown that they also contribute to a broad range of policy areas of other ministries. It is therefore important to involve several ministries beyond our ministry of Education, Culture and Science.

⁴ ELIXIR is organised as a 'Special Project' of EMBL; ERINHA and EBRAINS have been set up as AISBL

(international non-profit association under Belgium law).

Currently, we estimate that the costs for the operation of the Dutch LMS research infrastructures are well above EUR 100 million per year. A sizable 70% of these costs are taken on by Dutch Research Performing Organisations, whilst approximately 15% is secured through European (e.g. Framework Programme) and other national funds. An additional 15% is still to be acquired to ensure that the RIs can participate in the equivalent European LMS RIs in a sustainable manner. This includes the national memberships. Such additional investments can also help improve interoperation between national LMS-RIs, and help seed further development of nationally needed new research services and resources.

We call upon our National Government (multiple ministries) to contribute to the structural annual operational costs of our European LMS RIs, including the national membership fees, as a way of spreading the costs fairly among national RI service beneficiaries. Such commitment will ensure the sustainable provisioning of our services portfolio to science and national policy dossiers.

3.2 Research field contributes strong infrastructure resources and arranges for national node coordination

3.2.1 Strong Dutch infrastructure resources

The extensive participation of the Netherlands in European LMS research infrastructures established in the framework of ESFRI is a clear sign of the quality and maturity of the Dutch research infrastructure field. National strength built up in the field is the basis for this international participation and offers the national ticket to co-design and implement international research infrastructures. This

then ensures access to the broader field of Dutch life and medical scientists to advanced *international-grade* research facilities, resources, and related services, strongly supporting Dutch science and policy agendas as described above.

The Netherlands has, over the past decades, established a robust network of local and national research facilities, reflecting its strong international position in research and innovation across life and medical sciences. This network has developed largely through bottom-up initiatives, emerging in fields of research in which the Netherlands historically has had a strong presence, such as in molecular and cellular biology, in health and medical science, as well as in plant biology and biodiversity research. In these cases, establishment of shared research facilities has been driven by researchers at universities, university medical centres and research institutes, all with a commitment to opening up the latest technologies, information and materials to a wide range of scientists in the country.

Development of the research facilities key infrastructure resources as well as the day-to-day operation of the infrastructures is largely guaranteed through contributions from the academic partners that drive the development of these research facilities and resources. Over the years, the field already has contributed tremendously to this component with substantial investments and in-kind contributions covering management, data collection, establishing operational processes and continued provisioning of services to scientific communities. These have been funded from a variety of sources, ranging from institutional funding to national (incl. NWO, e.g. Roadmap Large-scale Research Infrastructures) and EU funding, in some cases also with support from industry. In its 2017 [Golden Principles for Research Infrastructures](#),

The League of European Research Universities (LERU) already supports this “mixed funding model for RIs”.

The collective investments in shared LMS research facilities have never been quantified in detail, but investments that are core to the national nodes of the European LMS RIs amount to several hundreds of million euros, with continuous annual investments from all field parties involved. The collective national arrangement we plead for will build on these strong contributions by research organisations to cover a large part of the sustainability of research infrastructures for the years to come.

“We call upon our National Government (multiple ministries) to contribute to the structural annual operational costs of our European LMS RIs, including the national membership fees, as a way of spreading the costs fairly among national RI service beneficiaries.”

3.2.2 National node coordination

Over the past decade, the field of research infrastructures has grown towards more coordination and integration of efforts at the national level. There have been several drivers for this organisation, for example because of the necessary alignment among distributed expert centres (typical in the LMS field) as part of European research infrastructures, or

because they are growing to a scale that exceeds the (financial) capabilities of a single research performing organisation. Such coordination is essential to synergise efforts and optimally position national activities in the international landscape.

Coordination of national nodes in the framework of European LMS infrastructures requires domain-specific experts. They have a role that goes beyond their personal scientific career, securing effective communication among the national community of specialised expert centres, with national infrastructure stakeholders and scientific users. Mature infrastructures thus all have a dedicated national team taking charge of scientific and technical leadership and strategy, community-support and communication, as well as administrative and process management to secure alignment with the agenda, reporting and organisational framework of the European research infrastructure. This then enables the joint and coordinated provisioning of facility access and prioritising required investments.

National node coordination of infrastructures has over the years been provided either in-kind by academic organisations acting as coordinators of the national communities, or in some cases by dedicated organisations, funded by and acting on behalf of the academic organisations (e.g. through contributing expert capacity in-kind). We expect this model to continue, although we foresee an opportunity for much more efficiency by bundling the coordination activities between multiple nationally organised research infrastructures through an improved Coordination and Support mechanism (see next chapter).

4.

Consolidation strategy to ensure long-term impact of European LMS RIs

A Bruker 950 US² NMR spectrometer is shown in a laboratory setting. The machine is a large, white, cylindrical unit with a blue logo and text. The logo consists of a stylized atom with three orbiting electrons. The text 'BRUKER' is in a bold, sans-serif font, and '950 US²' is in a larger, bold, sans-serif font. The machine is mounted on a metal frame. The background shows a laboratory with various pieces of equipment and a staircase on the right.

BRUKER
950 *US*²

4. Consolidation strategy to ensure long-term impact of European LMS RIs

4.1 Value proposition of collaboration and orchestration

As 15 national LMS-research infrastructures, we are committed to enhance mutual collaboration and to push for a strong, sustainable, integrated national LMS-RI ecosystem. The collaboration and orchestration of the Dutch national landscape of research infrastructures indeed provide a formidable value proposition. Through strategic and operational alignment of our national infrastructures, we will enhance innovation, promote knowledge sharing and establish a strong substrate supporting cross-disciplinary research. It will further provide avenues for avoiding overlap and building a collective and complementary portfolio of research services.

Especially in the Life and Medical Sciences domain, the Netherlands has a vibrant ecosystem of infrastructures that together deliver value towards a wide portfolio of more than 20 high policy priorities (see Chapter 2). These infrastructures rely on closely related data, technology and expertise that span across the whole spectrum of biological systems, from the molecular and organismal to the ecosystem levels. Strengthening the interoperation of our national LMS RIs can accelerate impact delivery and improve the

efficiency of their operation through models that enable the use of shared resources and the provision of joint services. This paves the way to extend international collaborations and research funding opportunities along those lines.

Through shared investments in data, facilities and services we can further optimise existing national investments and increase the capacity of Dutch LMS RIs to tackle complex research challenges and deliver measurable impact in crucial domains, such as medicine and public health, agriculture or nature conservation. Furthermore, a unified enabling environment can focus on growth and adaptation of the constituent RIs towards targeted national interests.

Achieving such a level of collaboration and interoperation will rely on developing a national **Coordination and Support mechanism** that can foster economies of scale and amplify the collective impact of RIs.

“As 15 national LMS research infrastructures, we are committed to enhance mutual collaboration and to push for a strong, sustainable, integrated national LMS-RI ecosystem.”

4.2. Sustainable funding and impact evaluation

Sustainable funding models are essential for our research infrastructures' long-term success and resilience. These models must be adaptable to the evolving needs of the scientific community and responsive to the outcomes achieved. Equally important is establishing robust mechanisms for evaluating the value of these infrastructures for science and their impact on society.

Currently, the Dutch ecosystem of RIs is sustained through the investments by the scientific community combined with a project-based approach that is essentially too short-lived to guarantee strategic continuity. Such projects are a crucial component in the life cycle of infrastructures, driving their initial development and supporting innovation, but they do not support sustainability nor foster longer-term return on the initial investment.

A longer-term strategic mechanism is needed, where RIs can sustainably operate in an open innovation environment that does promote tangible impact delivery. Regular assessment of performance metrics and impact delivery will ensure transparency, accountability, and the continuous alignment of our infrastructures with national and European research priorities. This evaluative process is critical in justifying ongoing investments and demonstrating tangible benefits of research activities to stakeholders and society.

4.3. National coordination and support mechanism

The strategic coordination of Dutch research infrastructures impacts multiple national

agendas, including health, innovation, education, and economic development. Establishing an orchestration and monitoring mechanism is imperative to effectively manage these impacts and ensure they contribute positively to our scientific and societal goals.

“A longer-term strategic mechanism is needed, where RIs can sustainably operate in an open innovation environment that does promote tangible impact delivery.”

We call for the joint development of a national Coordination and Support mechanism for LMS Research Infrastructures that involves all key actors including LMS infrastructures research organisations, ministries, funders (e.g. NWO, incl. PC-GWI) and other stakeholders. Such a strategic process should be set up to ensure the national sustainability of internationally connected Dutch LMS research infrastructures and do so in a well-coordinated and aligned manner with broader scientific and governmental agendas. The proposed national coordination and support mechanism must serve as the pivotal strategic process to design an integrated national LMS research infrastructure of the highest quality. The coordination and support mechanism should also drive the collective organisation, monitoring, and innovation of the Dutch LMS RI landscape. It will help enhance the visibility, accessibility and performance of our LMS infrastructures in support of a strong LMS-scientific community and a thriving and resilient society.

We propose to assign the following functions to the national Coordination and Support mechanism for LMS RIs:

Strategic Planning and Development

- Develop, in collaboration with the national scientific community and RI stakeholders, a long-term strategy for the development and sustained operation of the wider landscape of RIs, identifying gaps and interfaces.

Stakeholder Engagement

- Liaise with national stakeholders, including ministries, funders, and other academic organisations, promoting the use of RIs and translating user needs into service requirements.
- Foster collaboration of RIs within and across domains.

Financial and Sustainability Management

- Ensure sustainable co-funding of the Dutch RI landscape, including national node services and the financial obligations of the Netherlands as member state in corresponding European RIs.

Economies of scope and scale

- Identify strategic interfaces and collaborative operational trading zones (including joint projects, data, services, practices and processes) and reduce unnecessary redundancies between RIs.
- Develop and implement action plans for shared resources and connected services.
- Enhance the competitiveness of Dutch science and infrastructure in the context of the European funding landscape.

Monitoring and Evaluation

- Develop a national impact evaluation framework and monitor performance and impact delivery in relation to national scientific and societal needs.

Knowledge and Technology Exchange

- Help optimise visibility and accessibility of existing LMS RIs.
- Promote knowledge and technology exchange across national RIs and their European counterparts.
- Secure effective participation (and funding) in strategic European initiatives and driving research and infrastructure projects to Dutch stakeholder⁵.

The proposed LMS RI Coordination and Support mechanism, can provide a holistic view of our research infrastructure ecosystem, facilitating optimal decision-making and resource allocation and moving beyond the current short-term project-based approach.

“We call for the joint development of an inclusive national Coordination and Support mechanism for LMS Research Infrastructures”

For this process, learnings may be taken from a few existing cases of already strongly coordinated and organised national research infrastructure initiatives that have meanwhile been developed in the Dutch LMS field, to

⁵ e.g. 1+ Million Genomes Initiative, European Open Science Cloud, European Health Data Space and other European data spaces, European Missions,

European Green Deal, Digital Decade programme and the Biodiversity strategy 2030.

synergise national activities and harbour national nodes of multiple European research infrastructures. For example Health-RI ('enabling data driven health and life sciences research'), coordinating national nodes of currently three European LMS-RIs: ELIXIR (life science data infrastructure), BBMRI (biobanks and cohorts) and EATRIS (supporting translational medicine research), possibly extending to include EIRENE (supporting exposome research). Also, eLTER-LIFE (ecosystem research) brings together the resources developed by the national node of LIFEWATCH with the ecosystems monitoring data collected on the Dutch sites by eLTER.

In conclusion, the strategic orchestration and robust collaboration of the Dutch research infrastructures under a unified framework can significantly enhance our national capability in science and technology. With a sustainable funding mechanism, regular impact evaluation, and close alignment of LMS-RIs in the framework of a national coordination and support mechanism, the Netherlands will develop a very strong and coherent research infrastructure. This will position the Netherlands at the forefront of science and innovation, in support of our society.

“The proposed LMS RI Coordination and Support mechanism, can provide a holistic view of our research infrastructure ecosystem, facilitating optimal decision-making and resource allocation and moving beyond the current project-based approach.”

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Annex

Overview of contributions of individual European LMS Research Infrastructures to important national policy dossiers

	RI	DiSSCo	eLTER	EMPHASIS	IBISBA	LifeWatch	MIRRI
Topic	Natural science collections	Ecosystem monitoring	Plant phenotyping for sustainable food production	Industrial biotechnology & biomanufacturing	Biodiversity & ecosystem monitoring	Microbial resources	
Scope	Green Life Sciences	Green Life Sciences	Green Life Sciences	Green Life Sciences	Green Life Sciences	Green Life Sciences	Green Life Sciences
ESFRI status	Preparatory	Preparatory	Implementation	Preparatory	Operational 2017	Operational 2021	

OCW	Dutch Research Agenda (NWA)	●	●	●	●	●	●
	NWO Research grants: projects, programs, talent	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Infrastructures (landscape, clusters, international collaboration)	●	●	●	●	●	●
EZ	Biomolecular & Cell Technologies: Biosystems & Organoids; Biomanufacturing and Bioprocessing, Bioinformatics			●	●		●
	Imaging technologies: generating, collecting, analyzing, modifying and visualization of images, software and hardware	●				●	
	Artificial Intelligence and data: AI, Data Sciences, Data analytics and Data Spaces, Digital Twinning and immersive technologies	●			●	●	
I&W	Biotechnology, Compliance by Design, Safe by Design				●		●
	Water management, food production		●			●	●
	Climate change and sustainability	●	●			●	
LNVN	Sustainable agriculture, food safety and security	●	●	●	●	●	●
	Nature conservation, biodiversity	●	●	●		●	●
VWS	One Health						
	Health care innovation						
	Biotechnology and biosecurity				●		●
	Patients' privacy: European Health Data Space, secondary use of health data						
	Public health and One Health, antibiotic resistance	●					●
	Psychoactive compounds						

	RI	BBMRI	EATRIS	EBRAINS	EIRENE
Topic	Biomedical data and material collection, data & image and IT tools, ELSI, QM and training		Ecosystem monitoring	Plant phenotyping for sustainable food production	Industrial biotechnology & biomanufacturing
Scope	Medical & health		Medical & health	Medical & health	Medical & health
ESFRI status	Operational 2015		Operational 2013	Operational 2021	Preparatory

OCW	Dutch Research Agenda (NWA)	●	●	●	●
	NWO Research grants: projects, programs, talent	●	●	●	●
	Infrastructures (landscape, clusters, international collaboration)	●	●	●	●
EZ	Biomolecular & Cell Technologies: Biosystems & Organoids; Biomanufacturing and Bioprocessing, Bioinformatics	●	●	●	●
	Imaging technologies: generating, collecting, analyzing, modifying and visualization of images, software and hardware	●	●	●	
	Artificial Intelligence and data: AI, Data Sciences, Data analytics and Data Spaces, Digital Twinning and immersive technologies	●		●	●
I&W	Biotechnology, Compliance by Design, Safe by Design				
	Water management, food production				●
	Climate change and sustainability				●
LVVN	Sustainable agriculture, food safety and security				●
	Nature conservation, biodiversity				
VWS	One Health	●	●		●
	Health care innovation	●	●	●	●
	Biotechnology and biosecurity	●	●		
	Patients' privacy: European Health Data Space, secondary use of health data	●	●	●	●
	Public health and One Health, antibiotic resistance	●	●		●
	Psychoactive compounds	●	●	●	

	RI	EU-OPENSREEN	ERINHA	Euro-BioImaging	INSTRUCT	ELIXIR
Topic		Open screening platforms	BSL3 and BSL4 high-biocontainment laboratories	Microscopy and (bio)medical imaging	Structural biology	Life Sciences data & bio-informatics
Scope		Life Sciences & Enabling Technologies	Life Sciences & Enabling Technologies	Life Sciences & Enabling Technologies	Life Sciences & Enabling Technologies	Transversal
ESFRI status		Operational 2018	Operational 2017	Operational 2019	Operational 2017	Operational 2013

OCW	Dutch Research Agenda (NWA)	●	●	●	●	●
	NWO Research grants: projects, programs, talent	●	●	●	●	●
	Infrastructures (landscape, clusters, international collaboration)	●	●	●	●	●
EZ	Biomolecular & Cell Technologies: Biosystems & Organoids; Biomanufacturing and Bioprocessing, Bioinformatics	●	●	●	●	●
	Imaging technologies: generating, collecting, analyzing, modifying and visualization of images, software and hardware		●	●	●	●
	Artificial Intelligence and data: AI, Data Sciences, Data analytics and Data Spaces, Digital Twinning and immersive technologies		●	●	●	●
I&W	Biotechnology, Compliance by Design, Safe by Design	●	●		●	
	Water management, food production				●	●
	Climate change and sustainability		●			
LNVN	Sustainable agriculture, food safety and security					●
	Nature conservation, biodiversity					●
	One Health		●		●	●
VWS	Health care innovation				●	●
	Biotechnology and biosecurity	●	●		●	●
	Patients' privacy: European Health Data Space, secondary use of health data			●		●
	Public health and One Health, antibiotic resistance	●	●		●	●
	Psychoactive compounds	●				

